

ISic3293

I.Sicily inscription 3293

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μνημ[εἶλονένθάδεκίτεθεοχάρ]

2. ις Τ[--- ΟΥΔ][---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645560

PHI 316278

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 198
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 77.b = Libertini (1981) 124

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